

SELECTIVE GROWTH OF MICRO SCALE GAN INITIATED ON TOP OF STRIPE GAN

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1. Introduction

The energy bands of III-nitride-based structures grown along the [0001] direction of the wurtzite structure are strongly affected by substantial quantum confined stark effect (QCSE) and piezoelectric polarization [1-3]. The fields can cause significant separation of the electron and hole carrier wave functions and a red shift of the recombination energy. Internal electric field caused by spontaneous polarization and piezo effect can be eliminated by growing devices on non- or semi-polar facets of GaN crystals based on selective area growth (SAG) of III-nitrides [4-6]. Recently, three-dimensional GaN micro structures with non- or semi-polar micro facets are utilized as base structures for the development of white light sources by using of growth characteristics that the indium composition and growth rate of InGaN layers varied depend on crystalline orientations [7-8]. However, in these methods, laterally propagated threading dislocations initiated from the interface between substrate and GaN template can reach the inclined semi-polar facets where on InGaN/GaN multi quantum wells (MQWs) be grown. In this case, the deterioration of radiative recombination efficiency by the threading dislocations is unavoidable. Therefore, new methods for the formation of three dimensional GaN microstructures are needed to suppress the propagation of threading dislocations.

In this work, we propose a novel technique for selective growth initiated only on top area of triangular shaped GaN stripes (hereafter, we call it lower GaN stripes). This approach can be effective growth method to realize literally three dimensional structures which available for many applications. The evolution of well aligned selectively grown GaN stripes (hereafter, we call it upper GaN stripes) which including {11-22} facets was realized only on

top of the lower GaN stripes by selective epitaxial MOVPE growth. Reduction of threading dislocation and relaxation of strain can be expected because of small window area for the selective growth. In this report, we introduce detailed fabrication process for the formation of the upper GaN stripes on top of the lower GaN stripes. Distribution of crystalline defects was evaluated by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and room temperature cathodoluminescence (CL).

2. Experimental

Figure 1 shows a schematic illustration of the fabrication procedure for the upper GaN growth on top of the lower GaN stripes. Firstly, the lower GaN stripes were selectively grown by metal organic vapor phase epitaxy (MOVPE) on a GaN template with SiO₂ stripe patterns (window : 3 μm, mask : 7 μm) oriented along the <1-100> direction. TMG (trimethylgallium) and NH₃ were used as precursors for the gallium and nitrogen sources. Reactor pressure was maintained at 760 Torr and N₂ was used as carrier gas. The typical flow rates of TMG and NH₃ were 82 μmol/min and 3 slm, respectively. The growth temperature and growth time were 770 °C and 90 min, respectively. After the formation of the lower GaN stripes, SiO₂ film was deposited on the lower GaN stripes and followed by photo-resist (PR) coating as shown in Fig. 2. Thickness of the PR near top of the lower GaN stripes is thinner than other areas because of inclined facets of the lower GaN stripes. Chemical bonding of composites of the PR near top of the lower GaN stripes can be changed by relatively short duration of UV exposure while the other thick part of the PR may not have enough time to be completely changed. Because of the difference in chemical structure and thickness, the PR only near the top area can be removed by proper

develop time. Final selective growth was performed at 770 °C after removing the SiO₂ on top of the lower GaN stripes. Typical flow rates of TMG and NH₃ were 82 μmol/min and 3 slm, respectively. The growth time was varied from 1 to 60 min with constant reactor pressure of 760 Torr. Apart from the growth of the GaN micro-structures, we also performed a growth of GaN/InGaN multi-quantum well (MQW) structure on the semi-polar {11-22} facets of the upper GaN stripes to evaluate the possibility of applications of this new process to LEDs, LDs and other waveguide structures. The MQW structure was consisted of eight periods of InGaN/GaN layers grown at 800 °C and finally capped with 0.2 μm -thick GaN layer.

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 3 (a) shows the lower GaN stripes before the final selective growth was performed. The inclined side wall {11-22} facets show very smooth surface. SEM images of the upper GaN stripes are shown in figure 2 (b)-(d). Growth time of the upper GaN stripes were 1 min (Fig. 2 (b)), 10 min (Fig. 2 (c)) and 60 min (Fig. 2 (d)), respectively. The upper GaN stripes have triangular shape and the overall size increased with growth time. The growth rate in the direction of <11-22> gradually decreased with the growth time, from 2.5 nm/s (1 minute grown sample) to 0.5 nm/s (60 minutes grown sample). The entire surface area on which epitaxial growth take place will be increased with growth time and this can be the main reason of the reduced growth rate. We can see that the surface roughness of the upper GaN stripes is worse than that of the lower GaN stripes. This might be caused by undulated boundary lines of SiO₂ films. It is necessary to optimize the photolithography process to get smooth facet surface.

TEM image of the GaN stripes (60 minutes grown sample) was shown in Fig. 4. Many kinds of crystalline defects (including threading dislocation, edge dislocation, stacking fault) can be shown in the lower GaN stripes. However, the crystalline defects are remarkably reduced in the upper GaN stripes. This result is attributed to efficient blocking of the laterally propagating threading dislocations by SiO₂ mask and small window area for the selective growth. Although there are some stacking faults in the upper GaN stripe, but this new process is found to be an effective method to reduce crystal defects.

For more detailed analysis about the crystalline defects in the upper GaN stripes will be published elsewhere.

Figure 5 shows cross sectional monochromatic CL images of the upper GaN stripe and InGaN/GaN MQW structure grown on the upper GaN stripe. Fig. 5(a) shows a monochromatic CL image taken at 366 nm corresponding to the band edge emission of GaN. Crystal quality of the selectively grown GaN is gradually improved as the thickness of {11-22} facets increased. However the central area shows rather weak emission efficiency because of the crystal defects threading through the window area of the SiO₂ mask. Monochromatic CL image taken at 555 nm is shown in figure 5(b). Emitting area is mainly distributed in the central part of the upper GaN stripes where containing lots of crystal defects. Generally, yellow luminescence is attributed to deep donor states caused by Ga vacancy (or a related complex), carbon incorporation from metal organic sources and other origins [9-12]. From these results, it can be confirmed that the yellow luminescence is closely related to crystal defects even though there are many argues about the exact origin. Figure 5(c) shows a monochromatic CL image taken at 412 nm corresponding to the radiative transition of InGaN/GaN MQW. Spatially confined strong emission is observed near the top area of the upper GaN stripes. This quantum wire-like emission can be attributed to thicker quantum well width and higher indium composition in the top area compare to the other area in the {11-22} facets. The spatial inhomogeneous of quantum well thickness and indium composition is caused by the inhomogeneous growth rate and indium incorporation efficiency on the inclined {11-22} facets during the growth of InGaN/GaN MQW structure [13].

4. Conclusions

We successfully fabricated literally three dimensional GaN stripes only on top of the lower GaN stripes by newly developed process. However, more precise control of the photolithography process is needed to get smooth side facet for the application of high performance optical devices. Reduction of threading dislocation density was confirmed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) in the selectively grown upper GaN stripes. It is confirmed that the crystal quality of the upper GaN stripes is

gradually improved as the thickness of {11-22} facets increased. MQW structure grown on the upper GaN stripes shows spatially confined emission near the top region of the MQW structure. Although we need more optimized process to reduce crystal defects including threading dislocations in the central area of the three dimensional GaN stripes, this new method can be effective approach for the increase of radiation efficiency in optical devices such as LEDs and LDs because the selective growth was performed on semi-polar {11-22} facets. Furthermore, this crystal growth method can be applied for the fabrication of optical waveguides and non-phosphor white LEDs based on three dimensional structures with less crystal defects and strain by the small window area for the selective growth.

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Fig. 1. Schematic illustration of the fabrication process for the formation of upper GaN stripes.

Fig. 2. Cross-sectional SEM image of the photo-resist coated on the lower GaN stripes.

Fig. 3. SEM images of the upper GaN stripes : lower GaN stripe before selective growth of the upper GaN stripe (a), growth time 1 min (b), growth time 10 min (c) and growth time 60 min (d).

Fig. 4. TEM images of the GaN stripes (a) upper GaN stripe and (b) lower GaN stripe (scanning area are marked by square).

Fig. 5. Monochromatic CL images of the upper GaN stripe and the InGaN/GaN MQWs structure taken at (a) 366 nm, (b) 555 nm and (c) 412 nm.

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